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31 Data Availability Statement

32 All data are available in the supplemental materials or from the corresponding author.

33 Ethics Approval Statement

34 No ethics approval was required for this research.

35 Author Contributions

36 KRS conceived of the study, performed data collection and formal analysis, and wrote
37 the original draft of the manuscript. SLT, AMB, MTS, and JM conceived of the study and
38 reviewed and edited the manuscript.

39

40 Abstract

41 Dental caries is one of the most common diseases afflicting modern humans and has been
42 found to occur in both living and extinct non-human primates, as well as other mammalian
43 species. Compared to other primates, less is known about the etiology or frequency of caries
44 among diverse members of Strepsirrhini. Given the link between caries and diet, caries formation
45 and frequency may be informative about the dietary ecology of a given animal. Understanding
46 rates of caries in wild populations is also critical to assessing dental health in captive
47 populations. Here, we examine caries frequency in a sample of 36 extant strepsirrhine species (n
48 = 316 individuals) using odontological collections of wild-, non-captive animals housed at the
49 American Museum of Natural History by counting the number of specimens characterized by the
50 disease. As a case study, we also describe caries in two fossil strepsirrhine species for which
51 caries has not previously been identified: the earliest late Eocene *Karanisia clarki*, and the
52 subfossil lemur *Megaladapis madagascariensis*. Our results suggest that caries affects 13.92% of
53 the extant individuals we examined, with the majority of the lesions being found in the molars.
54 The frugivorous and folivorous taxa were characterized by the highest overall frequency of
55 caries, whereas the insectivores, gummivores, and omnivores had much lower caries frequencies.
56 *Eulemur* species, primarily frugivores, were characterized by the overall highest frequency of
57 caries. Our results suggest that caries may be common among wild populations of strepsirrhines,

58 and in fact is more prevalent than in many catarrhines and platyrrhines. These findings have
59 important implications for understanding caries, diet, and health in living and fossil taxa.

60 Introduction

61 Dental caries (or cavities) is among the most common diseases affecting modern humans,
62 with nearly every adult affected by caries at least once during their lifetime (Adler et al., 2017).
63 There are several factors that can contribute to caries such as oral health, oral biochemistry and
64 physiology, and dental morphology. The disease commonly occurs as a result of oral bacteria
65 present within the mouth consuming sugar-rich starches on the teeth, which lowers the pH in
66 localized regions, causing demineralization and eventual loss of the dental tissues (Lovell, 1991;
67 Crovella & Ardito, 1994; Miles & Grigson, 2003; Adler et al., 2013). The disease manifests as
68 concentrated areas of demineralization and eventually as permanent and local openings or holes
69 in the enamel and potentially the dentine, which may eventually penetrate the pulp cavity.
70 Because their formation depends in part on the presence of sugars, caries may provide
71 information about the diet of an individual or a species. Caries is not a disease unique to humans
72 and has been described in several species of wild animals including badgers (*Meles*), olingos
73 (*Bassaricyon*), coatis (*Nasua*), bears (*Ursus*), manatees (*Trichechus*), wild boars (*Sus*), mule deer
74 (*Odocoileus*), spear-nosed bats (*Phyllostomus*), wombats (*Vombatus*), and several non-human
75 primates (Crovella & Ardito, 1994; Miles & Grigson, 2003). For example, caries has been found
76 in high levels in some primate taxa such as in species of *Cebus* and *Saimiri* (Lovell, 1991), and
77 interproximal caries on the anterior teeth have been reported in high prevalence in taxa such as
78 *Cercopithecus denti* and *Presbytis femoralis* (Towle et al., 2022). However, little is known about
79 caries prevalence in one major radiation of living primates, the strepsirrhines. One study
80 mentions that of 650 lemur skulls, only 2 exhibited caries, though it is not known which taxa
81 were examined or which had caries (Miles & Grigson, 2003). Likewise, Crovella and Ardito
82 (1994) examined caries frequency in 11 genera of strepsirrhines, including lemurs, lorises, and

83 bushbabies. Of the 80 individuals they examined, 6 exhibited caries (7.5% of individuals).
84 However, they did not provide data clarifying which taxa were characterized by caries. Extensive
85 work has been done to document changes through the lifespan in the dentition of ring-tailed
86 lemurs but similar studies are not available for other strepsirrhine species (Cuozzo et al., 2010;
87 e.g., Cuozzo & Sauther, 2006, 2012; Sauther et al., 2002, 2006). More research is needed into the
88 frequency of caries among strepsirrhines, particularly as caries frequency in captive
89 strepsirrhines may be a potential indicator of the health in these animals (Cabana & Nekaris,
90 2015; Plesker & Schulze, 2013). For example, previous work has demonstrated that
91 strepsirrhines fed with an inappropriate diet may develop high levels of caries (Cabana &
92 Nekaris, 2015; Plesker & Schulze, 2013). Therefore, caries frequency in wild taxa could be used
93 as established baselines that may help determine when caries frequency increases beyond what is
94 expected for a member of that species. Consequently, studying caries frequency in wild animals
95 can provide important context for improving the welfare of captive animals.

96 Caries is not only a phenomenon observed in extant taxa but has also been observed in
97 several extinct primate and other mammalian (see Selig & Silcox, 2021; Towle et al., 2024) and
98 non-mammalian taxa (e.g., Kear, 2001). For example, Fuss et al. (2018) described a carious
99 molar of a Middle Miocene dryopithecine hominid dated to about 12.5 million years ago. Towle
100 et al. (2021) also described caries in several more recent fossil hominids including *Paranthropus*
101 *robustus*, *Australopithecus africanus*, *Homo naledi*, and early *Homo*. Han and Zhao (2002)
102 examined caries in *Gigantopithecus blacki*, which is described as having a high rate of caries
103 compared to other hominids. Selig and Silcox (2021) recently described what is the largest and
104 earliest collection of carious individuals in the fossil record; a sample (77 individuals with caries)
105 of the stem primate plesiadapiform *Microsyops latidens*, which is known from the early Eocene

106 (~54 million years ago). As case studies, here we describe three fossil specimens representing
107 two fossil strepsirrhine taxa characterized by the presence of similar lesions as those described in
108 the sample of extant strepsirrhines; *Karanisia clarki* and *Megaladapis madagascariensis*.

109 *Karanisia clarki* is known from the earliest late Eocene (~37 million years ago; Seiffert et
110 al., 2005) of Egypt and is represented by a mandibular fragment (analyzed and imaged here) and
111 isolated upper and lower teeth (López-Torres et al., 2020; Seiffert, 2012; Seiffert et al., 2003).
112 This taxon is the first to possess an undisputable toothcomb, meaning it is an extinct strepsirrhine
113 (Seiffert et al., 2003). However, the relationship of *K. clarki* to other strepsirrhines is contested,
114 with some evidence that the taxon belongs to the Lorisidae (Seiffert et al., 2003), that it is instead
115 a stem strepsirrhine (Seiffert et al., 2018), a crown strepsirrhine (Seiffert, 2007), a stem lorisoid
116 (Seiffert, 2007), or even a stem lemuroid (Seiffert et al., 2018). Nonetheless, it is clear that this
117 taxon represents one of the earliest crown strepsirrhines and therefore provides the oldest known
118 evidence for dental caries among crown primates. The dietary adaptations of *Karanisia clarki*
119 have been studied by measuring shearing quotients (Marivaux et al., 2013), using dental
120 topographic analysis (Fulwood et al., 2021; Patel et al., 2017), and by measuring enamel
121 distribution on the anterior dentition (López-Torres et al., 2020). Results suggest that the taxon
122 likely ate some combination of fruit and insects, potentially as an omnivore, and may have also
123 consumed gums.

124 *Megaladapis madagascariensis* is a much more recent taxon, likely having gone extinct
125 within the past 1,500 years (Burney et al., 2004; Marciniak et al., 2021). Typically described as a
126 giant subfossil lemur, *M. madagascariensis* is estimated to have weighed an average of 45.6 kg
127 (Jungers et al., 2008) and is predicted to have been folivorous, with a similar diet to modern

128 *Avahi* and *Lepilemur* based on dental microwear analysis (Godfrey et al., 2004). Caries in a
129 subfossil lemur is not known to have been described in the literature to this point, therefore, this
130 specimen provides further insight into caries in primates and strepsirrhines.

131 The goals of the present study are to examine caries presence among extant
132 strepsirrhines, to determine which taxa are characterized by the disease, and to determine how/if
133 diet is a mediating factor in its presence. We examined caries frequency in odontological
134 specimens taken from wild populations representing several extant strepsirrhine taxa to better
135 understand caries frequency among these animals and to better understand the relationship
136 between diet and caries. We also describe caries in three specimens representing the two fossil
137 taxa described above, which add to the still sparse record of primate fossils that are documented
138 to exhibit caries.

139 Materials and Methods

140 All specimens analyzed here are housed and curated in the Department of Mammalogy
141 and the Division of Paleontology at the American Museum of Natural History (AMNH), New
142 York, USA. Additionally, micro-CT scans of two specimens of the fossil taxon *K. clarki* (DPC
143 21249: Media ID 000036202 [no DOI assigned]; DPC 21636E: doi:10.17602/M2/M39083),
144 housed at the Division of Fossil Primates of the Duke Lemur Center (DPC), were downloaded
145 from MorphoSource (Boyer et al., 2016). The sample of extant taxa (n = 316 individuals)
146 includes 36 strepsirrhine species representing members of Lorisidae, Galagidae, Lemuridae,
147 Cheirogaleidae, Lepilemuridae, and Indriidae (Table 1). Specimens included were previously
148 wild-caught and died in their natural environments. All specimens are osteological, meaning no
149 live animals were included in this research. Specimens included in the analysis, as well as the

150 location of each carious lesion, are listed in the Supplemental Data. Specimens were included
151 only when all of the second molars (upper and lower) were fully erupted such that the majority
152 of the permanent dentition was present in all included taxa. By the time the lower second molar
153 is erupted, the included individuals should have been weaned (Smith et al. 1994) and would
154 therefore be prone to developing caries. Specimens were also only included if the majority
155 (>75% of the teeth) of the teeth were present, meaning specimens that lacked a mandible or were
156 characterized by several missing teeth, for example, were not included. Although the entire
157 collection at the AMNH was studied for many species, not all specimens in the AMNH
158 collection were included in the analysis because of missing teeth, etc. In some cases, extreme
159 dental wear (near-complete obliteration of the cusps) was observed (n = 16 individuals), and it is
160 possible that attrition could have removed caries previously present in these specimens.
161 Therefore, specimens characterized by high levels of wear are noted as such in the Supplemental
162 Data. The specimens of *K. clarki* we include are a right mandibular fragment preserving p4-m2
163 and alveoli of i2-p3 (DPC 21249) (Figure 1), as well as an isolated right M2 (DPC 21636E)
164 (Figure 2). The specimen of *M. madagascariensis* (AMNH 30022) we include was previously
165 collected from Madagascar, on the coast 60 miles north of Toliara and is a fragment of the right
166 mandible with m1-m3 present (m = lower molar, M = upper molar), as well as the alveolus of p4
167 (Figure 3).

168 The presence of caries was examined using a Nikon Stereo SMZ-1B 7x-30x microscope.
169 Caries ranged in severity from small pit-like lesions in the tooth surface, to near complete
170 obliteration of the occlusal surface, although no teeth with the pulp chamber exposed were
171 observed. We observed caries in the range of 1 and 2 using the 1-4 severity scale of Connell and
172 Rauxloh (2003). Changes in coloration were not used as criteria to assess caries (following

173 Towle et al., 2021) as not all cavitations were associated with a change in color (see Fig. 4a).
174 This is a conservative approach, but was deemed necessary based on variation in the coloration
175 of the museum specimens that made criteria based on color hard to apply consistently. Only
176 cavities that have already formed cavitations in the hard tissues were counted as demineralization
177 of the tissue in early caries could not necessarily be observed. Lesions between teeth are difficult
178 to observe using this method, so it is possible that they may have been missed. As a forming
179 carious lesion spreads, it tends to inflate inwards as it reaches the softer dentine, so we looked for
180 smooth, rounded, and inflated features, which helps distinguish from breakage or damage. Some
181 specimens were also micro-CT scanned using a GE v|tome|x s 240 dual tube 240/180 kV system
182 (General Electric, Fairfield, CT, USA) in the Microscopy and Imaging Facility of the AMNH.
183 Scanned specimens include AMNH 101510 (*Nycticebus javanicus*), and AMNH 269908
184 (*Perodicticus edwardsi*) (Figure 4), as well as the specimen of *M. madagascariensis*. The
185 specimens of *K. clarki* were scanned on the Nikon Metrology XT H 225 ST micro-CT scanner at
186 the Duke Shared Materials Instrumentation Facility at Duke University.

187 Each extant taxon was assigned to a dietary category (frugivore, omnivore, insectivore,
188 folivore, gummivore) based on the food source that each taxon spends the majority of their time
189 consuming, as documented in the literature (Tables 1 and 2). It should be noted that broad dietary
190 categories such as those above do not reflect variation in diet; therefore, these categories should
191 be considered as broad generalizations at best. To test for an association between the
192 presence/absence of caries and if there are any particular taxa and any dietary guilds that have
193 more caries than might be expected, we used chi-squared tests. We used an alpha value of 0.05
194 and calculated the adjusted residuals with a 95% confidence interval of ± 1.96 (Sharpe, 2015).
195 Given that many of our samples are small for certain taxa, we also performed an Ordinary Least

196 Squares (OLS) regression to determine the effect of sample size on our count of caries frequency
197 for each taxon we included. The chi-squared tests and the regression were performed using
198 PAST 4.02 (Hammer et al., 2001).

199 Results

200 Results of the analysis are summarized in Table 1 and Figures 5 and 6. Of the 316
201 strepsirrhine individuals examined, 44 (13.92% of the individuals examined) were characterized
202 by caries, with 25 (56.82%) of those individuals exhibiting more than one lesion. All individuals
203 with caries had the m3 erupted. Several species did not show any caries, such as *Otolemur*
204 *carissicaudatus* (n = 31) or *Galago moholi* (n = 22), whereas other taxa had a high percentage of
205 individuals with caries such as *Eulemur rufus* (n = 12; 33.33% of individuals), *Nycticebus*
206 *coucang* (n = 5; 40.00% of individuals), and *Loris lydekkerianus* (n = 3; 66.67% of individuals).
207 When grouped by diet (Figure 6), caries prevalence ranged from 4.55% among omnivores to
208 22.22% among frugivores. Results of the chi-squared test suggest that there is a significant
209 association between caries absence/presence ($X^2 = 51.74$, $p = 0.0339$) based on the species-level
210 analysis. The adjusted residuals suggest that *Propithecus verreauxi*, *Eulemur rufus*, *Eulemur*
211 *collaris*, and *Loris lydekkerianus* have significantly more caries than would be expected, whereas
212 *Otolemur carissicaudatus* has significantly fewer (Table S3). The dietary-level chi-squared test
213 also suggests that there is a significant association between caries absence/presence and diet (X^2
214 $=11.536$, $p = 0.0212$). The adjusted residuals suggest that frugivores have significantly more
215 caries than expected (Table S4).

216 The results of the OLS regression suggest that there is indeed a weak yet significant
217 relationship between sample size and caries frequency ($p = 0.0084$), however, the R^2 value is low

218 ($R^2 = 0.1872$) suggesting that although sample size does have an effect on caries frequency, that
219 effect is also low as well.

220 Caries position is recorded in the Supplemental Data (Table S2) by specimen. Overall
221 patterns suggest that occlusal caries is by far the most common form of the disease, with 94 of
222 the 99 carious lesions being occlusal (94.95% of total caries). Only 3 interproximal lesions were
223 identified. The presence of interproximal caries was noted on the right M1 in a specimen of
224 *Cheirogaleus medius*, the right P4 in a specimen of *Eulemur albifrons*, and the right M1 in a
225 specimen of *Eulemur collaris*. A single buccal lesion was noted on the right m1 in a specimen of
226 *Eulemur rufus*, and a single lingual lesion was noted on the right m1 of *Eulemur cinereiceps*. It
227 should be noted that not only is *Eulemur* characterized by the greatest diversity in caries type,
228 but as a genus, represents 15 of the 44 (34.01%) individuals with caries (and 10 out of the 25
229 [40.00%] individuals with more than one lesion), more than any other represented genus.

230 Carious lesions are distributed almost evenly between antimeres, with 50 lesions on the
231 right side and 48 coming from the left. However, they are not distributed evenly between the
232 upper and lower dentitions among individuals. Of the 44 individuals showing caries, 34
233 (77.27%) individuals show only upper caries, 6 (13.63%) show caries only on the lower
234 dentition, and 4 (9.09%) individuals have both upper and lower caries.

235 The micro-CT scans of *K. clarki* and *M. madagascariensis* (Figs. 1-3) provide the ability
236 to virtually dissect the teeth and to gain insight into the internal morphology of the teeth and the
237 effects of caries formation. The mandibular specimen of *K. clarki* is characterized by both an
238 occlusal caries on the m2 and an interproximal caries on the m1. Both of these lesions are
239 characterized by the presence of tertiary dentine, which can be seen in the endocast of the pulp

240 cavity leaving impression in the pulp (Figure 1). Dentine is deposited on the roof of the pulp
241 cavity (which creates the depressions in the endocast) to help protect the delicate and sensitive
242 internal tissues within the tooth such that they do not become vulnerable to infection (Figure 1).
243 The M2 specimen (Figure 2) shows a less progressed caries, which does not seem to penetrate as
244 deeply as the mandibular lesions.

245 The specimen of *M. madagascariensis* is characterized by a lesion on the m3 that
246 penetrates deeply into the pulp (Figure 3). This is a far more progressed lesion than those
247 observed in *K. clarki*. Given that this would leave the internal vessels and nerves exposed to the
248 oral cavity and any accompanying oral bacteria or food, this could very easily lead to infection in
249 this animal.

250 **Discussion**

251 Compared to other living primates, less is known about caries frequency among wild
252 strepsirrhines. Although several other studies have documented dental disease among wild ring-
253 tailed lemurs (Cuozzo et al., 2010; e.g., Cuozzo & Sauther, 2006, 2012; Sauther et al., 2002,
254 2006), dental disease and particularly caries frequency afflicting other strepsirrhines have largely
255 gone unstudied. Although this may reflect our use of a microscope to diagnose caries, whereas
256 previous studies have not always employed such techniques (see Corvella & Ardito, 1994; Miles
257 & Grigson, 2003), we found that 13.41% of the specimens examined showed evidence of caries,
258 a number much higher than previous data would suggest for this group ([7.5%] Corvella &
259 Ardito, 1994; [0.31%] Miles & Grigson, 2003). Given the relatively conservative criterion used
260 here for identifying caries (i.e., changes in coloration in the absence of an actual hole-like lesion
261 were not used) we can infer confidently that the number of individuals with some degree of

262 disease is likely higher. It should also be noted that younger individuals are less likely to exhibit
263 caries, meaning our samples, and particularly the small species samples, may be biased in one
264 way or another. Future work should also consider the relationship between age and caries
265 formation wherever possible. Generally speaking, our results suggest that not only do
266 strepsirrhines have more caries than previously thought, but some taxa have caries in higher
267 frequency than most other extant primates (see Selig and Silcox, 2021 table S1). The only extant
268 taxa with comparable instances of caries frequency to the strepsirrhines we examined with high
269 levels of caries are the frugivorous platyrrhines. For example, *Cebus* (26.80%) and *Saimiri*
270 (17.90%) (Lovell, 1991) have similarly high levels of caries as our well-sampled taxa such as *N.*
271 *javanicus* (21.05%) and *E. albifrons* (27.27%).

272 Although caries frequency was high in some taxa such as *Nycticebus coucang* (n = 5;
273 40.00% of individuals) and *Loris lydekkerianus* (n = 3; 66.67% of individuals), these samples
274 were quite small, and these results should be taken with caution. For example, *Nycticebus*
275 *javanicus*, an ecologically similar loris species to *Nycticebus coucang* (i.e., both are primarily
276 gummivorous), with a more robust sample size (n = 19), shows nearly half of the caries
277 frequency of *Nycticebus coucang*. Given the weak yet significant relationship we found between
278 sample size and caries frequency, future research should aim to include larger samples wherever
279 possible.

280 Our results point to the species of *Eulemur* as the most likely to be afflicted by dental
281 caries. Perhaps this is related to the more generalist diet with a higher proportion of fruit intake
282 of *Eulemur* compared to more specialized taxa such as the lorises (Table 1). It is the frugivorous
283 taxa that are indeed characterized by the higher overall frequency of caries compared to the

284 folivores, insectivores, omnivores, and gummivores. This is not surprising given that fruit tends
285 to be high in carbohydrates (sugar), which are a primary food source for carious bacteria. What
286 may be surprising is the relatively low frequency of caries among the gummivores, which also
287 consume high levels of sugars, or that not all highly frugivores species in the dataset have high
288 incidences of caries. For example, behavioral data suggest that *N. bengalensis* spends the largest
289 portion of its time feeding on gums compared to other gummivorous taxa, however, no
290 specimens (n = 6) show evidence of caries. *Euoticus* (n = 11) spends about 75% of its time
291 foraging for exudates, as does *N. coucang* (5), however, *Euoticus* is not characterized by any
292 caries, whereas *N. coucang* has a high incidence of caries. A difference between these taxa lies in
293 the fact that *Euoticus* consumes very low levels of fruit (5% of time spent feeding), whereas *N.*
294 *coucang* consumes far more fruit (22.5-71% of time spent feeding) Perhaps the low incidence of
295 caries among gummivores is explained by gums requiring little to no mastication and therefore
296 spending little time in contact with the enamel surface of the teeth.. Differences may also be
297 explained in the types of fruit consumed and the relative levels of sugars present in those foods.
298 They may also be related to the evolutionary history of the taxon including changes to enamel
299 thickness or microstructure, or to the oral microbiome, and the degree to which they are adapted
300 over long periods to eating fruit.

301 The folivores also showed relatively high frequencies of carious lesions. Although leaves
302 contain fewer sugars, the fact that leaves are generally tougher and may therefore require high
303 levels of oral processing compared to most fruit, and are more likely to cause dental attrition,
304 may leave the teeth prone to caries formation relative to other dietary regimes. The fact that
305 even the most folivorous primates consume some level of fruit (see Table 1) may mean that they
306 are still consuming sugary foods in addition to their abrasive folivorous diet. For example,

307 although we consider *Propithecus verreauxi* and *Indri indri* to be folivorous (Table 1), these
308 species consume the first and second highest proportions of fruit and are characterized by the
309 first and second highest frequency of caries among our folivore sample. Our findings highlight
310 the fact that primate diet is complex, and that the simple dichotomies of folivores vs. frugivore
311 are not always enough to characterize their diet.

312 Anthropogenic effects are also known to play a crucial role in the dental health of wild
313 strepsirrhines (Cuozzo et al., 2010; Cuozzo & Sauther, 2006, 2012; Sauther et al., 2002, 2006).
314 For example, *Lemur catta* living in highly disturbed regions are characterized by high levels of
315 severe dental wear and attrition resulting from their increased reliance on introduced tamarind
316 pods, whereas *Lepilemur*, which do not eat the hard pods of the tamarind but instead their leaves,
317 do not exhibit the same degrees of dental wear (Cuozzo & Sauther, 2012). Therefore, a direct
318 link between folivory or frugivory and dental health may a far more complex matter than the
319 simple dichotomy suggests, particularly in anthropogenically disturbed contexts. Overall, our
320 findings have implications for interpreting the diet of fossil taxa, which have been shown to have
321 high caries frequency in some cases (i.e., Selig and Silcox, 2021). Although the presence or
322 absence of caries does not provide much information about diet, high caries frequency may
323 indicate that the taxon consumed high levels of simple sugars.

324 Of the 99 identified carious lesions, only 3 were interproximal and none were observed in
325 the toothcomb teeth or in the upper canines and incisors. This is unlike the pattern observed in
326 catarrhines, where the vast majority of the observed carious teeth were among the anterior
327 dentition (Towle et al., 2022). This difference may, in part, be related to the fact that many
328 catarrhines frequently use their anterior teeth to peel fruit, during which fruit fibers may become

329 lodged between the teeth (Towle et al., 2022), while the strepsirrhine toothcomb is not
330 universally adapted for food preparation. Additionally, strepsirrhines use their toothcomb to
331 groom, during which several hairs pass in between the anterior teeth and could potentially
332 remove any trapped food, thus reducing the likelihood of caries formation. Strepsirrhines (and
333 tarsiers) also uniquely possess a sublingua, which is an anatomical structure located below the
334 tongue that is usually associated with cleaning the toothcomb (Saint-Hilaire & Cuvier, 1824;
335 Nekaris, 2014; Pastor et al., 2021). This structure may provide an additional means for
336 preventing the formation of caries in the anterior dentition in strepsirrhines. We should also note
337 that acidic foods becoming trapped in the teeth, and particularly in the occlusal basins, could also
338 lead to the formation of pit-like features that are not technically carious in their etiology.
339 However, acid erosion is reportedly rare in non-human primates. For example, Dumont (1997)
340 notes that frugivores seem to buffer against acid erosion with high salivary pH, a result that is
341 supported by Cuzzo et al. (2008), who document that *Lemur catta* also has an alkaline pH that
342 is believed to buffer the effects of consuming highly acidic tamarind pods.

343 Future research is needed examining strepsirrhine caries formation, frequency, and
344 severity in other wild specimens. Although our research includes 37 extant species, it represents
345 only a fraction of the diversity of described strepsirrhine taxa. Moreover, the present sample
346 consists exclusively of odontological specimens, and of unknown age. With ever-increasing
347 anthropogenic effects on strepsirrhines, research on living populations is needed to fully
348 understand the process and consequences of caries formation in these animals. Given that the
349 dentition is an indicator of health in both captive and wild populations (Cabana & Nekaris, 2015;
350 Cuzzo et al., 2010; Cuzzo & Sauther, 2006, 2012; Plesker & Schulze, 2013; Sauther et al.,
351 2002, 2006), further research on caries in wild populations will have important implications for

352 the welfare of captive primates. Future research should also consider how age and wear play
353 roles in the frequency of caries in wild strepsirrhines.

354 Our paper also presents new insight into caries in extinct primates. We provide evidence
355 for caries in two species for which the disease is newly described, as well as the earliest evidence
356 of caries in crown Primates. It is noteworthy that the mandibular specimen of *K. clarki* is
357 characterized by an interproximal carious lesion given how rarely they occur in our extant
358 sample. The presence of carious lesions and the presumed diets of *K. clarki* (frugivore/omnivore;
359 Marivaux et al., 2013; Patel et al., 2017; López-Torres et al., 2020; Fulwood et al., 2021) and *M.*
360 *madagascariensis* (folivore; Tattersall, 1975; Godfrey et al., 1997, 2004; Jungers et al., 2002;
361 Rafferty et al., 2002; Scott et al., 2009; Muchlinski et al., 2011) are consistent with our findings
362 among extant strepsirrhines in that the frugivores and folivores present the highest frequency of
363 caries. As more specimens are recovered and more collections are examined for the presence of
364 caries, it is likely that many other species will be diagnosed with caries. The study of caries in
365 fossil and subfossil taxa has the potential to shed light on the life history of particular extinct
366 individuals. For example, although the individual of *Megaladapis* analyzed here does not show
367 signs of major infection, the lesion would likely have been impaired the health of the animal and
368 could ultimately have reduced fitness. This kind of observation adds texture to our understanding
369 of extinct individuals, and provides a unique window into their lives.

370 Statement of Ethics

371 No ethics approval was needed for this study.

372 Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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568 Figure Legends

569 Figure 1. Three-dimensional reconstruction of the mandibular specimen of *K. clarki* (DPC
570 21249). **A.** In buccal view showing caries on the second molar (white arrow) and the
571 interproximal lesions on the first molar (grey arrow). **B.** In occlusal view showing caries on the
572 second molar (white arrow) and the interproximal lesions on the first molar (grey arrow). **C.**
573 Virtual endocast of the second molar pulp cavity showing a depression (white arrow) where
574 tertiary dentine was deposited in the roof of the pulp in response to caries formation. **D.** Virtual
575 endocast of the first molar pulp cavity showing a depression (grey arrow) where tertiary dentine
576 was deposited in the roof of the pulp in response to caries formation. **E.** The same as C. in
577 occlusal view. **F.** The same as D. in occlusal view. **G.** The same as D. and F. in occluso-distal
578 view. **H.** The same as C. and E. in occluso-distal view. Scale bar = 1 mm.

579 Figure 2. Three-dimensional reconstruction (left) and micro-CT scan slice through the carious
580 lesion (right) of the upper molar specimen of *K. clarki* (DPC 21636E). White arrow denotes the
581 lesion. Scale bars = 1 cm.

582 Figure 3. Three-dimensional reconstruction and photograph of the specimen of *M.*
583 *madagascariensis* (AMNH 30022) in **A.** occlusal and **B.** buccal views. Virtual endocast of the
584 third molar pulp cavity showing the depth of the lesion in **C.** occlusal and **D.** buccal views. Scale
585 bars = 1 cm.

586 Figure 4. Three-dimensional reconstruction and photographs of **A.** *Nycticebus javanicus* (AMNH
587 101510) and **B.** *Perodicticusedwardsi* (AMNH 269908) with carious lesions demarcated by the
588 white arrows. Scale bar = 1 mm.

RH: Dental Caries in Living and Extinct Strepsirrhines

589 Figure 5. Column graph plotting the percent of individuals characterized by the presence of
590 caries at the species-level. Number of specimens examined are in brackets.

591 Figure 6. Column graph plotting the percent of individuals characterized by the presence of
592 caries at the dietary-level. Number of specimens examined are in brackets.

A.

C.

B.

D.

Species-Level

Dietary-Level

Table 1. Species included in the analysis, number of specimens studied are in brackets, percent of individuals characterized by caries, and proportional dietary data are included where available.

Family	Species (n = number studied)	% Caries	Diet	Proportions of feeding time	Reference
Galagidae	<i>Galagoides demidoff</i> (9)	0.00%	Insectivorous	19% fruit, 10% exudates, 70% insects	(Bearder, 1987)
	<i>Galago moholi</i> (20)	0.00%	Insectivorous	48% exudates, 52% insects	(Bearder, 1987)
	<i>Galago senegalensis</i> (23)	8.70%	Insectivorous	48% exudates, 52% insects	(Burrows et al., 2020; Harcourt, 1986)
	<i>Otolemur crassicaudatus</i> (31)	0.00%	Gummivorous	33% fruit, 62% exudates, 5% insects	(Bearder, 1987; Harcourt, 1986)
	<i>Otolemur garnettii</i> (6)	0.00%	Omnivorous	50% fruit, 50% insects	(Bearder, 1987)
	<i>Sciurocheirus alleni</i> (5)	0.00%	Omnivorous	50% fruit, 50% insects	(Burrows & Nash, 2010)
	<i>Euoticus elegantulus</i> (11)	0.00%	Gummivorous	5% fruit, 75% exudates, 20% insects	(Nash, 1986)
	Lorisidae	<i>Nycticebus coucang</i> (5)	40.00%	Gummivorous	75% exudates, 22.5-71% fruit, 2.5-29% insects
<i>Nycticebus bengalensis</i> (6)		0.00%	Gummivorous	92.9% exudates, 0.3% fruit, 1.9% bark, 2.9% invertebrates	(Swapna et al., 2010)
<i>Nycticebus javanicus</i> (19)		21.05%	Gummivorous	53.28% exudates, 15.82% fruit, 19.85% insects, 8.17% flowers, 1.93% leaves	(Cabana et al., 2017)
<i>Nycticebus kayan</i> (2)		0.00%	Gummivorous		
<i>Loris lydekkerianus</i> (3)		66.67%	Insectivorous	60% exudates, 40% insects	(Streicher, 2009)
<i>Loris tardigradus</i> (3)		33.33%	Insectivorous	96% insects	(Nekaris and Bearder, 2007)
<i>Perodicticus potto</i> (3)		33.33%	Frugivorous	100% insects	(Nekaris and Bearder, 2007)
<i>Perodicticus edwardsi</i> (13)		23.08%	Frugivorous		
<i>Perodicticus ibeanus</i> (15)	13.33%	Frugivorous	67% fruit, 22% exudates, 11% insects	(Burrows et al., 2020)	
	<i>Varecia rubra</i> (3)	0.00%	Frugivorous		

Lemuridae	<i>Varecia variegata</i> (4)	0.00%	Frugivorous	87.82% fruit, 6.07% flowers, 0.96% leaves, 3.38% young leaves	(Vasey, 2002)
	<i>Eulemur albifrons</i> (22)	27.27%	Frugivorous	74% fruit, 26% leaves	(Beeby & Baden, 2021)
	<i>Eulemur sanfordi</i> (3)	0.00%	Frugivorous	68.89% fruit, 13.06% flowers, 5.32% leaves, 6.46% young leaves	(Vasey, 2002)
	<i>Eulemur cinereiceps</i> (3)	33.33%	Frugivorous	76% ripe fruit, 4% unripe fruit, 5% young leaves, 1% mature leaves, 13% flowers	(Chen et al., 2016)
	<i>Eulemur collaris</i> (11)	36.36%	Frugivorous	99.8% fruit	(Sato et al., 2016)
	<i>Eulemur rufus</i> (12)	33.33%	Frugivorous	77.6% fruit, 8.8% leaves, 10.0% flowers	(Sato et al., 2016)
	<i>Eulemur mongoz</i> (3)	0.00%	Frugivorous	25.83% unripe fruit, 51.33% ripe fruit, 12% mature leaves, 7% young leaves	(Simmen et al., 2006)
	<i>Eulemur rubriventer</i> (3)	0.00%	Frugivorous	65% fruit, 17% leaves, 14% flowers	(Sato et al., 2016)
	<i>Lemur catta</i> (11)	9.09%	Omnivorous	80.6% fruit, 13.6% leaves, 3.1% flowers	(Sato et al., 2016)
	<i>Hapalemur griseus</i> (10)	10.00%	Folivorous	20% unripe fruit, 37.33% ripe fruit, 19% mature leaves, 19.67% young leaves	(Simmen et al., 2006)
	<i>Lepilemur ruficaudatus</i> (5)	20.00%	Folivorous	88% bamboo and grasses, 4% non-bamboo foliage, 5% fruit	(Tan, 1999)
Lepilemuridae	<i>Lepilemur leucopus</i> (14)	7.14%	Folivorous		
	<i>Phaner furcifer</i> (2)	0.00%	Gummivorous	90.1% leaves, 4.4% flowers, 0.6% fruit	(Dröscher & Kappeler, 2014)
Cheirogaleidae	<i>Cheirogaleus major</i> (2)	0.00%	Frugivorous	65% exudates, remainder is equally divided between insects and fruit	(Nash, 1986)

	<i>Cheirogaleus medius</i> (3)	33.33%	Frugivorous	69% fruit, 23% flowers, 7% insects, 1% exudates	(Lahann, 2007)
	<i>Indri indri</i> (8)	25.00%	Folivorous	68% fruit, 23% flowers, 7% insects, 2% exudates	(Lahann, 2007)
Indriidae	<i>Avahi laniger</i> (5)	0.00%	Folivorous	72.3% young leaves, 16.4 fruit, 6.7 flowers	(Powzyk & Mowry, 2003)
	<i>Propithecus deckenii</i> (6)	16.67%	Folivorous	98.27% young leaves, 1.73% mature leaves	(Faulkner & Lehman, 2006)
	<i>Propithecus verreauxi</i> (12)	33.33%	Folivorous	64.9% leaves, 19.9% fruit, 8.6% flowers	(Sato et al., 2016)
